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ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT AND EMPLOYMENT GENERATION- A CASE STUDY OF RUDSET INSTITUTE IN KERALA

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Abstract:

As marching towards encompassing a high rate of growth with great potential of human resources, Indian economy struggling to utilise its man power because of lack of employment opportunity, absence of successful ventures etc. Poverty, social exclusion, inequality, and unemployment etc are still haunting Indian economy, despite a number of planned efforts made by both central and state government to mitigate them. Though, Kerala is rich with her natural endowment and high potential educated youth, still struggling to make the most out of them because of lack of successful entrepreneurship activities and absence of a favourable industrial climate. A large number of youth in rural and semi-urban Kerala could not access high professional education and employment due to financial constraint and their high orientation towards white colour jobs. The theory of development by Schumpeter highlighted the significant role played by entrepreneurs and their innovative and imperative role in the development process of the economy. Absence of credit, poor infrastructure, socio-economic backwardness due to some religious and cultural taboos and customs especially on women and marginal section etc acts as a barrier to the natural growth of entrepreneurship in India and Kerala. Both Central and State government initiated a number of programmes to foster entrepreneurial development. In 1982, an innovative initiative was taken by Sri. Dharmasthala Manjunatheswara Educational trust, Syndicate bank and Canara bank finally resulted in the setting up of a very well appreciated RUDSETI model in India to tackle unemployment issues in rural area by providing credit accessibility and skill development programmes for entrepreneurial development for the socially disadvantaged people mainly belongs to SC, ST, BPL and women. The present study is to analyse the organisational structure and functioning of RUDSETI of Kerala situated in Taliparamba and also to evaluate various Entrepreneurship Development Programmes (EDP) offered by the institute.

Keywords: Unemployment- Rudset- Entrepreneurship and skill development- Training- Motivation

1. INTRODUCTION

Unemployment in India is a major economic issue that impede the rate of growth of India over the years. World Employment and Social Outlook–Trends (2018) report by the International Labour Organization, released on 22 January 2018 says that “As many as 18.3 million Indians were unemployed in 2017, and this unemployment is projected to increase to 18.9 million by 2019”.According to a report first published in the Business Standard, an

Indian financial newspaper- India's jobless rate shot up to 45-year high during 2017-2018. NSSO showed unemployment rate at 6.1 percent, the highest since 1972-73- Joblessness stood at 7.8 percent in urban areas compared with 5.3 percent in the countryside.

Month/Year	India	Urban	Rural
Jan 2019	7.13	8.80	6.24
Dec 2018	7.38	7.64	7.25
Nov 2018	6.62	7.56	6.14
Oct 2018	6.91	7.27	6.72
Sep 2018	6.61	7.58	6.10
Aug 2018	6.32	6.81	6.06
Jul 2018	5.70	6.25	5.41
Jun 2018	5.81	6.77	5.30
May 2018	5.22	6.31	4.65
Apr 2018	5.64	6.31	5.29
Mar 2018	6.03	6.20	5.94
Feb 2018	5.93	6.72	5.52

Source :NSSO, 2019

The NSSO reports also highlights that, For rural male youth (aged 15-29) unemployment went from 5 percent in 2011-12 to 17.4 percent in 2017-18. For rural women in the same age group, joblessness went from 4.8 percent in 2011-12 to 13.6 percent in 2017-18. For educated rural females, the unemployment rate ranged from 9.7 per cent to 15.2 per cent during 2004-05 to 2011-12 which rose to 17.3 per cent in 2017-18. For educated rural males, the unemployment rate stands at 10.5 percent for 2017-18. The rate of joblessness for urban youths was a whopping 18.7 per cent for males and 27.2 per cent for females.

2. ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES –A TOOL TO ERADICATE UNEMPLOYMENT

Entrepreneurship has now become an important tool to eradicate unemployment and create new job opportunities for youth in both developed and developing countries. Indian government has taken a number of initiatives to eradicate unemployment. Entrepreneurial development programmes supplement the growth of micro small medium enterprises in India. MSM sector accounts for more than 95 percent of the industrial units and contributes 45 percent of the manufacturing output and 40 percent of the export (Ministry of MSME, 2014). Small enterprises play a crucial role in creating employment and helping in the industrialisation of rural and backward areas. For promoting the micro small and medium enterprises various policies, programs and schemes have been developed from time to time by state governments. In order to make Entrepreneurship the important component of state economy the government has taken various step to create awareness, entrepreneurship education, skill up gradation, knowledge dissemination, attitude modification and building consensus with national and international organizations.

3. REVIEWS OF LITERATURE

Morris et al. (2001) studied that entrepreneurship is a step-wise process affected by both exogenous and endogenous factors like presence of business friendly environment, required factor endowments, capability to acquire required resources, and implementation and management of business concept. Enormous studies highlighted the importance of entrepreneurship for eradication of unemployment issues, Drucker (1985) and Gorman et al. (1997), Alarape (2007, p. 225) Utterback and Reitberger, 1982. Watson et al. (1998) Vesper, 1985, Vesper and McMullen, 1988; Solomon and Fernald, 1991. Ronstadt, 1987; Katz, 2003; Solomon et al., 2002; Robinson and Hayes, 1991; Sexton and Upton, 1984-Kolvareid and Moen (1997). Studies made by Beck and Demirgüç, -Kunt (2006), IFC (2012) Kumar and Francisco (2005) pointed out that inadequate access to formal credit is one of the key bottlenecks for small enterprises. Entrepreneurs are majorly classified as necessity driven and opportunity driven. The necessity driven entrepreneurs are compelled by the adverse economic conditions while opportunity-driven are compelled by the new innovations and opportunities which they identify and perceive (Lehimer, 2013). The theory of economic development stages draws a direct link between entrepreneurship and innovation. Indeed, a shift in favour of opportunity entrepreneurship stimulates innovation. This result is also found in endogenous growth models such as the model of King and Levine (1993), inspired by the Schumpeterian approach. Orza (1988) discusses the major assumptions of Entrepreneurship Development Programmes (EDPs) and its rationale in the context of India. After a brief overview of the history of the EDP movement in India and its contribution to developing small-scale industries, he puts forward a methodology for the evaluation of EDPs. The educational background of entrepreneurs is not found to have too much bearing on their entrepreneurial pursuits whereas previous experience in the same product line was found to influence their performance. Nair et. al (1998) is by far the largest survey-based study on entrepreneurship in Kerala. Based on a field survey involving 300 rural entrepreneurs in Kerala, the study found that in the particular context of Kerala, contextual circumstances play a dominant role in facilitating entrepreneurship. The institutions created to support the growth of small-scale industries suffer from complex, cumbersome and bureaucratic practices and cause many problems for entrepreneurs. Drucker (1985) and Gorman et al. (1997) revealed that entrepreneurship education leads to the success of entrepreneurship. Alarape (2007, p. 225) described entrepreneurial learning as “the improvement of insights, knowledge, and associations between past actions, the effectiveness of those actions and future actions”. Lack of motivation and confidence hinders the entrepreneurial change; the education that leads to the creation of entrepreneurial skills and motivation (Utterback and Reitberger, 1982). Watson et al. (1998) concluded that personal background, motivation for start up and growth orientation leads to the success of any venture creation. Training in entrepreneurship has been carried out in many contexts (Vesper, 1985), but most of the training programmes focus on entrepreneurial abilities as business plan development (Vesper and McMullen, 1988; Solomon and Fernald, 1991). Recent studies have shown that entrepreneurship spirit among graduates is usually the outcome of entrepreneurship education (Ronstadt, 1987; Katz, 2003; Solomon et al., 2002; Robinson and Hayes, 1991; Sexton and Upton, 1984). Kolvareid and Moen (1997) opined that students who have taken a course or training in entrepreneurship have had shown greater interest in becoming entrepreneurs and act more entrepreneurially than other students in taking up the challenge to start a new business.

4. RESEARCH PROBLEM

Though, Kerala is rich with her natural endowment and high potential educated youth, still struggling to make the most out of them because of lack of successful entrepreneurship activities and absence of a favourable industrial climate in Kerala. A large number of youth in rural and semi-urban Kerala could not access high professional education and employment due to financial constraint and their high orientation towards white colour jobs. The theory of development presented by Schumpeter highlighted the significant role played by entrepreneurs and their innovative and imperative role in the development process of the economy. Absence of credit, poor infrastructure, socio-economic backwardness due to some religious and cultural taboos and customs especially on women and marginal's etc acts as a barrier to the natural growth of entrepreneurship in India and Kerala. Both Central and State government initiated a number of programmes to foster entrepreneurial development. The present study is about the RUDSET setup in India, an initiative undertaken in order to provide credit accessibility and skill development programmes for entrepreneurial development for the socially disadvantaged people in the rural India.

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study is based on the following objectives

- 1) To understand the nature of EDP courses offered in RUDSET
- 2) To analyse the impact of EDP courses on employment creation, credit accessibility and skill development among the RUDSET trainees

6. METHODOLOGY

Present study is focused on the RUDSET institute in Kannur district. The courses offered, stake holder's details etc are explored from both primary and secondary data. The major secondary source is the statistics collected from the Directors office, RUDSET of Kerala, situated in Taliparamba, Primary data is collected with the help of a questionnaire by interviewing 100 alumni's of RUDSET, Taliparamba.

7. RUDSET

In 1982, an innovative initiative was taken by Sri. Dharmasthala Manjunatheswara Educational trust, Syndicate bank and Canara bank finally resulted in the setting up of a very well appreciated RUDSETI model to tackle unemployment issues in rural area by providing credit accessibility and skill development programmes for entrepreneurship development to the socially disadvantaged people mainly belongs to SC, ST, BPL and women. RUDSET Institute has established 27 units across 17 states in India. The success of RUDSET Institute inspired Central Government to start more than 500 institutions under RUDSETI.

RUDSET Institute, Kannur – the only RUDSET Institute in Kerala was originally established in the year 1985 at Maipady in Kasaragod district, catering to the needs of the unemployed youth in Kasaragod, Kannur, Mahe and Wayanad district. In 1994 the Institute shifted to a rented building atKannapuram. In the year 2011 the institute has shifted to own campus at Kanhirangad, Near Taliparamba.

8. EDP COURSES OFFERED IN RUDSET

Entrepreneurship training has been depicted as one of the most important step for entrepreneurship development. The basic premise of entrepreneurship development is that entrepreneurship need not necessarily be an inborn trait. It is possible to identify individuals

with 'latent entrepreneurial traits' through the application of certain behavioural tools and techniques which can be imparted through specially designed training courses known as Entrepreneurship Development Programmes (EDPs). The following are the major EDP courses offered in RUDSET per year. All the courses are offered with free of cost and boarding facility is provided to the participants during the course duration.

- Women's tailoring(women only)- 30 days
- Computer hardware-45 days
- Goat rearing-10 days
- Business management(REDP)-13 days
- Poultry – 10 days
- Computer DTP-45 days
- Photography and videography-30 days
- Beauty parlor management (women only)-30 days
- House wiring-30 days
- Computerized accounting -30 days
- Dairy farming and vermi composing- 10 days
- Motor Rewinding and pump set repairing-30 days
- Four wheeler driving-30 days
- Aluminum fabrication-30 days
- Honey bee keeping- 10 days
- Mobile Phone servicing-30 days
- Two wheeler mechanic-30 days
- Men's beauty Parlor (Men only)- 30 days

The following table gives the details of Programmes offered by RUDSET and the rate of growth of participants attending these courses. 71.47 percent of total course participants are now employed (4963/6944).

Source : Office of the Director, RUDSET, Kannur, January 2019

Year	No. of EDP	No. of Course Participants	Male	Female
2011	20	594	265	329
2012	29	834	453	381
2013	31	946	480	466
2014	31	948	518	430
2015	33	947	592	355
2016	33	828	428	400
2017	35	910	612	298
2018	35	937	467	470
Total	247	6944	3815	3129

There is an increasing trend in the number of courses offered by RUDSET and the number of participants over the years from 2011 to 2018. On an average 28 members are added to each year compared to the previous period. Number of male participants outnumbers their female counterpart except in the year 2011 and 2018.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROFILE OF COURSE PARTICIPANTS

The status based report of the course participants shows that from 2011 to 2018, out of the total participants majority are from OBC category(48.37) followed by religious minorities(30.73), Sc (5.79) and St's(3.04)

Year	SC	ST	OBC	Minorities	others
2011	45	18	263	198	70
2012	41	12	434	238	109
2013	61	22	571	172	120
2014	66	34	439	289	120
2015	47	31	441	331	97
2016	51	29	359	278	111
2017	46	32	402	314	116
2018	45	33	450	314	95
Total	402	211	3359	2134	838

Source : Office of the Director, RUDSET, Kannur, January 2019

Details of the RUDSET trainee's shows that among the applicants, priority shall be given to BPL, socially disadvantaged and vulnerable sections and rest of the seats are allotted to APL category.

Year	Female			Male			Total		
	BP L	APL	Differentially abled	BP L	APL	Differentially abled	BPL	APL	Differentially abled
2011	123	206	-	113	152	2	236	358	2
2012	46	335	2	84	369	3	130	704	5
2013	179	287	1	97	383	2	276	670	3
2014	104	326	2	88	430	3	192	756	5
2015	114	241	1	135	457	5	249	698	6
2016	111	289	1	90	338	1	201	627	2
2017	60	238	0	113	499	0	173	737	0
2018	187	283	2	140	327	3	327	610	5
Total	924	2205	9	860	2955	19	1784	5160	28

Source : Office of the Director, RUDSET, Kannur, January 2019

It is quite evident from the sample that many of the aspirants are from APL category, lack of proper representation from the disadvantaged groups shows the very little awareness about the courses among the general public. .

ANALYSIS OF SAMPLE SURVEY

A sample survey is collected from 100 alumni's of the RUDSET institute in order to understand the impact of EDP on employment creation and skill development and credit accessibility, and the results are as follows.

Variable	Category	No of trainees
Age	Less than 25	17
	25-35	41
	35-45	25
	45-55	17
Gender	Male	58
	Female	42
Caste	Forward Caste	17
	Other Backward Caste	53
	Other Eligible Caste	5
	Scheduled Caste	22
	Scheduled Tribe	3
Religion	Hindu	64
	Islam	25
	Christian	11
Educational attainment	Up to SSLC	50
	PDC/Plus Two	36
	Degree	14
Marital Status	Single	47
	Married	53
APL/BPL	APL	39
	BPL	61
District	Kannur	97
	Other Districts	3
Region	Urban	17
	Rural	83
Family size	Nuclear family	84
	Joint family	16

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

Majority of the alumni's are belongs to the age category 25-35, a large number of participants are from Kannur district, though there is no strict regional priority is existing in the selection of candidates, there are very few aspirants appearing the interview for the selection process. Most of the trainees are having a high school education. Regarding the awareness about the RUDSET courses is given in the following table

	Frequency	Cumulative Percent
Friend and family	50	50

Print/Electronic media	28	78
Social Networks Sites	14	92
others	8	100.0
Total	100	

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

The factors that motivate a person to become an entrepreneur can be broadly classified into prime motivators, motives, compelling factor, facilitating factors and opportunity factors. A prime motivator refers to the entrepreneurs themselves and/or their friends or relatives. A question is asked to the alumni's that, from where they received the information regarding the RUDSET courses?. The answer depicts the role of friends and family and the very close network effects.

The major motives behind starting a new venture are to earn more money, to support one's family, to continue a family business or to achieve a higher social status. The factors that compel a person to start a new business can be unemployment or dissatisfaction with a particular job. Facilitating factors include the availability of idle funds at the entrepreneur's disposal, eagerness to make use of the skills the person has acquired over time, previous experience in the same line, support from friends or relatives, inherited property etc. The opportunity factors of entrepreneurship are trade information, business contacts, knowledge about sources of raw materials etc., and good education and training.

Table-6	
Motivating factors to Join RUDSET	
Factors	Frequency
To get business idea and to start a business	53
To gain knowledge and skills	25
For personal growth	8
Cost free course	11
Other reason	3
Total	100

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

The major motivating factor to join the RUDSET course is to gain knowledge about business. EDP has a direct impact on development of entrepreneurial skills in terms of business knowledge, drive and determination and communication. Primary data analysis of the sample study depicts that there is significant impact on trainees in terms of their entrepreneurship skills and competencies. Also training has impact on the development of managerial and competitive skills. Out of the total sample 94 percent of them said that EDP enhanced their business knowledge and self confidence 983 percent)

Skills	Mean/ percent	Std. Deviation	N
Business knowledge	.94	.232	100
Risk taking mentality	.72	.454	100
Self confidence	.83	.378	100
Leadership Ability	.67	.478	100
Entrepreneurial skill	.72	.454	100
Creativity and Innovation	.69	.467	100
Communication Skill	.69	.467	100

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

The above analysis is also checked for reliability with the help of reliability statistics Cronbach's Alpha, the value of the results shows high reliability in the statement of the trainees that it EDP helped them to improve their skills.

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items
.942	.931	7

The results of the study suggest that entrepreneurship By participating in entrepreneurship programs, owners/managers of small businesses learnt better managerial skills like pro-activity, creative tendency, drive and determination, and business knowledge which in turn lead to better performance of entrepreneurs and provide a unique competitive edge to the enterprises. However, the results have indicated that entrepreneurship training has great role in providing business knowledge and creation of self confidence but very least role in improving the leadership qualities and creative tendencies among the entrepreneurs. Thus a need is felt to make by the amendment in Entrepreneurship Development Training Programmes and include the leadership and creative tendency skills in the entrepreneurship course design.

9. EMPLOYMENT PROSPECTS

Out of the total 100 trainees interviewed, 53 are employed, and remaining 47 is planning to start a business in a short time span. The employment status of the respondents is given below

	Frequen cy	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Sole proprietorship	40	75.5	75.5
Partnership	11	20.8	96.3
Association	2	3.7	100.0
Total	53	100.0	

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

Sample analysis highlights that, 75.5 percent of the trainees are self employed and their major source of finance is bank loan. One of the interesting finding is that, RUDSET makes all the necessary arrangements to their credit accessibility with their tie-up institutions Syndicate bank and Canara bank.

Source of financing the business	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Own/self incurred	5	9.4	9.4
Bank loan	41	77.4	86.8
Loan from micro credit institution	4	7.6	94.4
Friends and family supported	3	5.7	100.0
Total	53	100.0	

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

9.4 percent of the alumni's raised their investment form own fund, 7.6 percent with the help of micro credit institution and the rest with the help of friends and family.

case		total investment incurred/expected	Monthly expenditure incurred/expected	Monthly returns received/expected
Course participant planning to start a business	Mean	125000.00	5705.88	17058.82
	No. of sample	47	47	47
	Std. Deviation	98425.09	7139.37	16868.87
Course participants already started a business	Mean	376315.79	22342.12	72236.84
	No. of sample	53	53	53
	Std. Deviation	350146.17	24410.87	108150.15
Total sample	Mean	257638.89	14486.11	46180.56
	No. of sample	100	100	100
	Std. Deviation	289261.34	20017.67	83221.92

Source : Primary survey conducted at RUDSET, Kannur on January 2019

The investment expenditure incurred by the person ranges from 1 lakh to 4 lakh, with a return of Rs. 1.5 to 7 lakh. The major issue related to the courses offered in RUDSET is the lack of awareness about the courses among the general public. Few are opting the courses

without much proper objectives, though it is offered at free of cost. Wrong selection of courses is also another issue faced by the participants. Centre is at the peak of its facility to accommodate new course participants, need encouragement and support from the centre and state government. RUDEST is taking some follow –up programmes through Correspondence, Branch Level Meet, Door to Door visit, Taluk level meet, Reply through Post Card, Unit Visit by the officials of the Institute by showing much concern for its stake holders.

10. CONCLUSION

Entrepreneurship Development Programme is designed to help an individual in strengthening his entrepreneurial motive and in acquiring skills and capabilities necessary for playing his entrepreneurial role effectively and also to make him enable to get an employment and lead a better life in the society. RUDSET has to widen its entrepreneurship development programmes by giving proper awareness about their courses among the less privileged sections of the society. The centre needed immense support from the government for its venture to eradicate unemployment problem among rural youth.

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